

Tools for the validation of ADAS functions in field operational tests

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ABSTRACT: The automotive industry is rapidly developing increasingly complex Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) functions targeting broader Operational Design Domains (ODD). Therefore, future safety assessments will need to go beyond proving ground testing and include further testing in simulation and open road. This work focuses on the potential use of Field Operation Tests (FOT) for the safety assessment of ADAS functions, proposing a set of semi-automatic tools to facilitate the planning, monitoring, and analysis of FOTs for ADAS functions. Given the ODD, we extract a set of known scenarios to test from a scenario database, maximizing the coverage of the ODD. These scenarios will be allocated to testing in either proving grounds, simulation or open road. The scenarios to be tested in the open road are then fed into the route planner that uses a route database to calculate the optimal route. In terms of data acquisition, we record Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data, Controller Area Network (CAN) data, and we mount a reference perception system based on cameras, radars and lidars to automatically detect the road lines and the trajectories of all the objects around the vehicle under test. A camera is also recording the dashboard to automatically detect the state of ADAS functions. A human annotator can optionally be in the vehicle with a tagging tool application to collect additional data, such as traffic signs, events or unexpected situations with different criticality levels. During the driving campaign, we perform an automatic monitoring of the progress so that we can adjust the route to have a higher probability of finding the expected scenarios and conditions before the driving campaign is over. Lastly, we update the scenario and route databases based on the scenarios and conditions found during the FOT. This methodology provides actionable insights for developers and objective safety evaluations in real driving conditions for regulators and agencies involved in the safety assurance of ADAS functions.

KEY WORDS: ADAS, CCAM, validation, testing, FOT, safety

Figure 1 Overall process of testing ADAS functions with a focus on the tools for field operation tests.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most current Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) functions are aimed at levels of automation between 1 and 3 as defined by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) [1], meaning the driver is either driving or may be requested to drive, if necessary. Assessing the safety of these functions has been mainly approached so far by testing concrete scenarios in proving grounds with extremely specific conditions. For example, to test an

Automated Emergency Braking (AEB) following Euro NCAP protocols, the vehicle is tested considering different speeds and trajectories in car-to-car scenarios as well as scenarios with vulnerable road users.

However, as the Operational Design Domain (ODD) of ADAS functions increases to include more complex scenarios, and different ADAS functions are available or active at the same time, this approach could be insufficient. Extrapolating the behaviour of the system, in all possible real-world scenarios and conditions in

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the ODD based on a limited number of concrete scenarios in proving grounds, seems unrealistic for functions with higher levels of automation, where the car drives itself without requiring continuous supervision from the driver.

Therefore, future safety assessments will need to go beyond proving ground testing and include further testing in simulation and open road. As shown in Figure 2, inspired from [2], proving ground and virtual testing can only be applied to a subset of the known scenarios and it can not be used to discover new unknown scenarios that are possible in the real-world. But Field Operational Tests (FOT) can target, although never fully cover, all scenarios in the ODD, including unknown scenarios.

Regulatory bodies and consumer testing programs are increasingly recognizing the importance of real-world validation and are incorporating FOT into their evaluation roadmaps [3]. While controlled proving ground testing provides baseline performance data, FOT drives offer valuable insights into how these systems perform under diverse real-world scenarios and environmental conditions. The significance of FOT data lies in its ability to validate ADAS functionality in uncontrolled environments, where diverse and unpredictable scenarios, that cause driver interventions or unexpected behaviour from the ADAS functions, emerge [4]. This real-world validation is essential for ensuring the safety and reliability of ADAS across varied ODDs.

While simulation and structured testing remain fundamental, real-world testing via FOT is crucial not only for exposing the system to a wide range of variations within known hazardous scenarios but also for identifying unknown hazardous scenarios that may not be captured in controlled testing. Continuous updates to scenario databases, informed by FOT results, can significantly enhance the robustness of ADAS validation.

From a consumer testing perspective, Euro NCAP is introducing the robustness concept in 2026 [5], which marks a shift in vehicle safety assessment. This new framework includes specific robustness layers focused on perception that can only be effectively evaluated through comprehensive FOT drives. Vehicle manufacturers will need to demonstrate compliance by providing detailed FOT information to Euro NCAP, specifically documenting various identified scenarios that correlate with these robustness layers. In this context, the availability of a reliable and sophisticated FOT tool becomes important, as it must accurately capture, analyse, and validate the complex interactions between vehicle systems and real-world conditions.

Implementing robust FOT methodologies will allow manufacturers to systematically assess and document vehicle system performance across diverse environmental conditions, traffic scenarios, and edge cases. This comprehensive approach to data collection and analysis will not only support regulatory homologations and Euro NCAP's assessment process but also drive continuous improvement in ADAS technology development, ultimately contributing to the organization's mission of promoting safer vehicles on European roads.

This work focuses on the potential use of FOT or the safety assessment of ADAS functions, proposing a set of semi-automatic

tools to facilitate the planning, monitoring, data management and analysis of FOTs for ADAS functions.

Figure 2 Venn diagram of the scenario space for testing.

2. Tools for ADAS FOTs

2.1. General Overview

We propose a complete pipeline, shown in Figure 1, going from a given ODD, planning and monitoring the route, acquiring and processing the data, analysing the results and extracting KPIs.

The first step in our process is to clearly establish which ADAS functions are going to be covered, and which is their ODD. Then, we can define a set of conditions or scenarios that the vehicle should be tested under for maximal cover of the ODD. This information is then fed into the route planner, where the driving campaign is designed considering the conditions and scenarios that we want to cover.

In terms of data acquisition, we record Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data, Controller Area Network (CAN) data, and we mount a reference perception system based on cameras, radars and lidars to automatically detect the road lines and the trajectories of all the objects around the vehicle under test. A camera is also recording the dashboard to automatically detect the state of ADAS functions. These data can then be used for an automatic analysis that detects events, based on triggering conditions, for manual review when there is an anomaly on the system under test or the vehicles around. A human annotator can optionally be in the vehicle with a tablet running a tagging tool application to collect additional data, such as annotating traffic signs or tagging unexpected situations with different criticality levels for manual review.

During the driving campaign, we can monitor the progress automatically, including following of the specified route, the correct acquisition of data, and the findings of relevant conditions and events. In this way, we can detect if some of the expected conditions and events are not being found and adjust accordingly to have a higher probability of finding them before the driving campaign is over.

Then we analyse the driving campaign in terms of the amount of time or kilometres driven in any given combination of conditions. This includes for instance the percentage of time a given ADAS function was activated while driving at night, and how many safety

incidents occurred during that time along with their criticality. Next, we provide more details on each component.

2.2. Route planner

The operational limits of the ADAS functions are described in the ODD. Therefore, the validation of an ADAS function involves performing the necessary tests to ensure that the function will be safe and robust within the conditions described in the ODD.

This includes different weather conditions, such as clear, rainy, foggy, snowy and stormy weather. It also involves different lighting conditions, such as daytime, nighttime, dawn, dusk, etc. Additionally, different road surface conditions must be considered, such as dry, wet, icy, snowy, etc. Regarding traffic and infrastructure, there is a broad variety of traffic conditions, such as different traffic densities, different road types such as highways, urban streets, rural roads, intersections, roundabouts, tunnels, bridges, etc. Different lane configuration such as single-lane roads, multi-lane highways, reversible lanes, construction zones, etc. It is also essential to evaluate if the system follows rules such as traffic lights, traffic signs, and roundabouts. And its interaction with other road users such as cars, pedestrians, bicyclists, motorcyclists, trucks, and emergency vehicles. Additionally, edge cases are of high relevance, including erratic driving or pedestrian behaviour, accidents or other emergency situations, GNSS signal loss and V2X or sensor failures.

Therefore, given an ODD and set of ADAS functions to test, the goal of the route planner is to find a route that maximizes the coverage of the scenarios in the ODD, including the discovery of unknown scenarios, subject to a certain number of testing days.

A route database stores information with an associated date, time and GNSS location. It contains information about where and when we found specific elements, events, conditions, or scenarios. Using this database along with generic map services, we can maximize the probability of having sufficient coverage. Once the route is planned, we can have some summary statistics and visualization such as the one shown in Figure 3, to make sure that the route is aligned with the purpose of the FOT.

Figure 3 Planned distribution of driven kilometres.

2.3. Data Acquisition

The data acquisition strategy used during open road testing is based on an adaptive data collection framework, tailored to the specific needs and objectives of the testing campaign. One approach consists of continuous recording: from the moment the vehicle is turned on until it stops, capturing all available data. This procedure results in a large volume of data, which can later be extracted to obtain detailed metrics, such as the total kilometres during which an ADAS function was active or available. However, this large dataset implies that significant post-processing is necessary to recognise specific events or situations of interest.

Alternatively, we can use an event-driven system that only initiates logging when specific triggers occur. An event trigger can be automatically generated, based on pre-determined thresholds indicating a safety-relevant event, or manually annotated by a test driver using a dedicated interface, such as the tagging tool described in subsection 2.7. When such an event occurs, the system stores the recording for a short interval of time around the event, for instance 30 seconds before the event and 10 seconds after. This alternative approach greatly reduces the amount of data stored and processed but limits the ability to continuously measure the overall exposure in a particular operating condition or the whole activation period of a particular ADAS system.

Each method has its own strengths. The continuous recording strategy delivers an exhaustive dataset, capturing all available data, which is ideal for deriving extensive performance metrics. In contrast, the event-triggered method concentrates on capturing only the most critical events, thereby reducing the overall data volume and enhancing processing efficiency. The choice between these approaches ultimately depends on the specific validation objectives and the available resources, ensuring that the data acquisition system can adapt to the testing requirements without compromising on quality or efficiency.

2.4. Cloud platform

Data acquisition generates vast datasets that require efficient storage, processing, and analysis. Cloud computing technologies enhance these processes by handling high workloads while ensuring scalability, security, and high availability. For cloud-based data processing, raw data from vehicle recordings can be stored in Amazon Simple Storage Service (Amazon S3), leveraging its scalability, durability, and performance. The data analysis pipeline, responsible for transforming raw data into structured formats for KPI extraction and scenario identification, can be packaged into a Docker image, stored in an Elastic Container Registry (ECR), and executed on Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) instances.

While local processing remains an option, its scalability is inherently limited. In contrast, the cloud environment provides dynamic resource allocation, allowing for parallel processing of large datasets, reducing processing time, and improving overall efficiency. This approach ensures that the analytical workflow can adapt to evolving validation needs without compromising performance or resource availability, being especially important when scaling to driving campaigns with multiple vehicles.

2.5. Reference Perception System

The behaviour of ADAS functions is mainly dependent on the position, size, velocity and acceleration of the vehicles and other road users around the vehicle under test, as well as the road lines, traffic signs and traffic lights. Therefore, to validate the performance of ADAS functions, it is necessary to have an accurate description of the static and dynamic objects in the scene. The static part, mainly lane markings and traffic signs can be extracted from a mapping service. The traffic signs and traffic lights can also be manually tagged by an occupant. And the weather can be obtained from an online service given the time and location. The more challenging information to obtain accurately is the dynamic information of the objects around the vehicle. To be able to robustly validate ADAS functions in open road testing, the reference perception system must be more accurate than the onboard perception of the vehicle under test. Otherwise, we could be falsely reporting incorrect behaviour due to an inaccurate estimation by the reference perception system. We follow two approaches to mitigate this risk. We mount redundant, multimodal and more accurate sensors that those mounted on commercial vehicles, that need to be cost effective, and process the data offline with more precise and computationally intensive algorithms. We then combine the detections from all the sensors and track them over time to get more robust estimations [6], as shown in Figure 4. Additionally, we include manual revision for the events of higher criticality, to make sure that our detections are accurate and to describe the unexpected behaviour in detail so that it is useful for developers.

Figure 4 Reference Perception System on highways.

2.6. ADAS state detection from a dashboard camera

The state of ADAS functions can be retrieved from CAN data if the database (DBC) file is available. However, DBC files are not public, therefore a more general alternative would make testing more accessible and allow benchmarking activities. Since the state of the ADAS functions is shown in the dashboard, a possible approach is to record the dashboard and extract the state automatically via computer vision. Given enough training data, an object detector such as a version of YOLO [7] could be trained to automatically detect the state of ADAS functions from dashboard images such as the one shown in Figure 5. Alternatively, we have implemented a simpler approach based on colour statistics that does not require training data and can be configured easily for a new vehicle model. To configure our method, we just need to select the region where each icon appears. We showcase an example in Figure 3 with two ADAS functions, an Automatic Cruise Control (ACC) and a Traffic Jam Assist (TJA), both with 4 possible states: turned off (no icon),

turned on (grey icon), stand-by (white icon), and activated (green icon).

To automatically extract the state of each ADAS function, we crop the area of the image corresponding to the function and calculate scores S_g and S_c , that represent how green the icon is and the contrast of the icon relative to the background respectively. Given the RGB image crop, S_g is the mean of the green channel divided by the mean of the red channel.

Given the grayscale image crop I_{gray} , and its mean μ_{gray} ,

$$P_{dark} = \{I_{gray}(x, y) \mid I_{gray}(x, y) < \mu_{gray} - 20\},$$

$$P_{bright} = \{I_{gray}(x, y) \mid I_{gray}(x, y) > \mu_{gray} + 20\}$$

Where P_{dark} are the dark pixels and P_{bright} are the bright pixels. If $|P_{dark}| = 0$ or $|P_{bright}| = 0$, then $S_{contrast} = 0$. This means that there is very low contrast in the image and therefore the icon is not present. Otherwise, we calculate the means μ_{dark} , μ_{bright} of P_{dark} and P_{bright} respectively and the contrast score as:

$$S_c = \frac{\mu_{bright} - \mu_{dark}}{100}$$

Then, the final state is

$$State = \begin{cases} Activated, & \text{If } S_c \neq 0, S_g \geq 1.2 \\ Stand - by, & \text{If } S_c \geq 1, S_g < 1.2 \\ Turned on, & \text{If } 0 > S_c < 1, S_g < 1.2 \\ Turned off, & \text{If } S_c = 0 \end{cases}$$

Figure 5 Dashboard image (left) and the automatic detection of the state of ACC (bottom-right) and TJA (top-right) for the sequences with more transitions. Green border for activated, blue for stand-by and red for turned on.

2.7. Tagging tool

Detecting all interesting events and relevant information automatically is not yet robust enough. Therefore, we can have a person in the vehicle manually tagging the relevant information. This could include traffic signs, traffic lights, type of road, specific scenarios, unexpected behaviour of the ADAS functions with different criticality levels, weather conditions, potholes, etc.

As shown in Figure 6, the tagging tool has a main view to select the category and then a specific view for that category. In this way, we can tag a large set of information pressing only 2 buttons and without the need to memorize codes. For a very specific event that is not included in the application, the user can input it in text.

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Figure 4 The tagging tool. General view on the left, and the speed view, which appears when clicking the speed button, on the right.

2.8. Scenario identification and extraction

Typical driving scenarios can be identified by analysing the trajectories of surrounding road users, the trajectory of the ego vehicle, and map information, using a logical approach. This includes recognizing logical scenarios from the scenario database such as lane changes, merges, overtaking manoeuvres, stop-and-go traffic, and intersection crossings. Additionally, anomalous or unexpected behaviours, such as sudden braking, swerving, or erratic lane changes, can be detected and categorized with a criticality factor.

Once these scenarios are identified, the trajectories are parsed into a standard format, such as ASAM’s Open Simulation Interface (OSI). The OSI trajectories can then be processed to generate an ASAM OpenSCENARIO file. Using GNSS data from the vehicle and HD maps, a standard ASAM OpenDRIVE file can be created to represent the static elements of the scenario, such as road geometry and lane configurations. These OpenDRIVE and OpenSCENARIO files represent a concrete scenario, a comprehensive and structured description of the driving scenario that can be reproduced in simulation and proving grounds, if necessary. We illustrate the process of converting the detections to scenario in Figure 7.

If the concrete scenario corresponds to a logical scenario in the scenario database, we can link them to analyse the frequency and criticality distribution of the logical scenario. And if it does not, the concrete scenario can be analysed, together with similar concrete scenarios, to create a logical scenario and include it in the scenario database.

Figure 7 Illustration of the conversion from raw data and detections (top) to scenario (bottom).

2.9. Driving campaign monitoring

Detecting missing data after the FOT is completed can be costly as it might involve a second FOT to gather the necessary data. Therefore, being able to detect it early is crucial. Specially in a multi-vehicle driving campaign, where not all drivers will be familiar with all the specific objectives of the FOT.

It is essential to monitor the status of each vehicle, including checking the data acquisition and route completion. Part of this monitoring is done in real time on each vehicle and part of the monitoring is done daily on the cloud. At vehicle-level, an automatic monitoring checks its location, adherence to planned routes, vehicle health and data acquisition status. This allows to report issues such as low battery, sensor degradation, missing data in the recordings and overall system integrity. Incidents detected in the vehicle are reported to the vehicle occupants and the remote supervising team immediately in order to solve them before continuing driving.

The data acquired in every vehicle is uploaded to the cloud every day so that the data can be analysed overnight. In this analysis we can extract the actual distribution of driven kilometres and visualize it like the planning distribution shown in Figure 3. This allows early detection of deviations from the target distribution so that we can replan the route prioritizing the events, scenarios or activations of ADAS functions that are further from the target.

2.10. Data Analysis. Key Performance Indicators

The vast volumes of data generated during open-road testing must be systematically processed into quantifiable metrics that provide clear insight into both the testing campaign and the system’s performance. In this context, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) serve as the basis for transforming raw data into meaningful information. On one hand, event-based criticality KPIs provide insight into the safety performance of the ADAS system by capturing the frequency and severity of critical events. Each event is assigned a criticality score on a scale from 1 to 5, where lower levels indicate minor associated risk, and higher levels denote safety-critical incidents. This scoring system enables continuous monitoring of both expected and unforeseen events within the test campaign. The frequency of these events, alongside their criticality levels, reflects the performance of ADAS systems and the overall safety strategy.

Quality classification of miles further refines the tracking process by assessing cumulative test miles based on the level of critical events encountered, the number of new edge case scenarios, the extent of ODD coverage, and overall system exposure. The monitoring of quality metrics allows comparisons with the target ratios established for effective validation, examines the distribution of miles in the test program and helps to generate recommendations for quality improvement, ensuring optimal use of test resources and complete validation coverage. Within this framework, three categories of kilometres are considered: high value kilometres are considered those that contain safety critical events (with criticality levels of 3 to 5), extreme case scenarios, show complex traffic interactions and typically occur at ODD limits; medium value kilometres represent mid-complexity ADAS operations, events with lower criticality (levels 1 to 2) and reflect normal traffic interactions, thus providing routine system exposure; and base value kilometres are accumulated under standard driving conditions with no significant events, capturing basic system functionality and overall exposure.

The integration of testing campaign tracking with event-based criticality KPIs ensures that the extensive data recorded during

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testing is transformed into a structured framework for validation. By quantifying both the breadth of environmental and operational exposure and the quality and frequency of critical events, including the appearance of previously unknown hazardous scenarios, manufacturers are able to optimise validation efforts and drive continuous improvements in ADAS safety and performance.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work we have presented our framework for field operational tests of ADAS functions. As ADAS functions become increasingly more complex and their validation relies more on field operational tests, others could benefit from any of the tools we have presented, and from their integration in the overall process proposed. We have left for future work the explanation of the scenario database and route database in detail, the allocation of scenarios to test in proving grounds, simulation and open road, as well as the analysis of the correlation between the behaviour of ADAS functions when tested under the same scenario in proving grounds, simulation and FOT. A standardised set of tools to test and validate ADAS functions would accelerate their development and acceptance by regulators and the public, so it is important to align between stakeholders while developing proprietary tools.

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